

Does Crossword Puzzle Rightly Cross the Brain of Medical Students?Kancharla Sirisha¹, Kanneganti Jhansi²¹Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, Mamata Medical College, Khammam, Telangana²Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Mamata Medical College, Khammam, Telangana

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Kancharla Sirisha

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: There has been a paradigm shift in the teaching, learning methodologies after CBME was introduced for undergraduate medical curriculum in 2019. It was designed aiming at better outcomes with practical proficiency of concepts learned in MBBS. Self-directed learning was introduced to sensitize and facilitate the student for andragogy and lifelong learning. Various methods of teaching like problem based learning (PBL), team based learning (TBL), ability based education were brought into limelight to aid in achieving andragogy. It will be thus good to know what students prefer and think about learning styles; thereby a faculty can plan a teaching session accordingly. Gamification is one of the novel tools where students enjoy learning with critical thinking and application of knowledge. The does level in the Bloom's taxonomy requires a good, knowledgeable physician who can apply the knowledge and act appropriately by applying the content learnt. Thus, it is inclusive to understand what the students perceive about learning methods like CWP.

Materials and Methods: This prospective study was conducted in the department of Physiology in April 2024 from at Mamata Medical College, Khammam. 66 students of first year MBBS participated voluntarily in the activity. After the routine teaching hours by one faculty dealing with all objectives on Endocrine physiology, a Google form comprising of 10 multiple choice questions pertaining to the objectives was circulated. A CWP activity on endocrine glands was conducted in the class. A follow up Google form was also sent after the group activity, for their views on it. A post test was conducted a week later by another Google form on the same competencies from endocrinology. Perceptions of students on CWP were analyzed; the pre and post-test scores were compared by chi-square test.

Results: There were a total of 66 students of which 35 were females and 31 were males. It was observed that more than 50% of the students had agreed to the usefulness of the activity for their learning. In the feedback obtained, 43.93% strongly agreed that the CWP activity was interesting, all gave an affirmation on group discussion on CWP gave a better understanding of the topic. The pre and post test scores showed significance of $p < 0.00001$, thus the post test scores improved after the CWP activity.

Conclusion: Students perceived that activities like CWP made learning interesting and made them think critically which will lay a good foundation if implemented regularly in the curriculum.

Keywords: Crossword Puzzle, Andragogy, Medical Education, Active Learning.

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Introduction

The traditional didactic lecture is an established effective passive learning method. Under CBME, as the focus is shifted to adult learning, the quest for better teaching learning methods which initiate self-learning have been in demand.[1] One of the goals for an ideal IMG (Indian Medical Graduate) is life- long learner.[2] It is the duty of a medical teacher to foster this habit in their students to ensure their andragogy continues for life.

Adult learning facilitates active learning, critical thinking on the students side whereas the teacher can use the time in the class more effectively to focus on the must know areas and thereby reinforce content for better understanding of the concept.[3]

Gamification has been useful to enhance retention of knowledge, reasoning abilities and application of medical concepts which are essential for future clinical practice.[4] Crossword puzzle is a tool that can make learning interesting, enjoyable and also stimulate critical thinking in the students.[5] CWP also helps in self-assessment of spellings of difficult terms involved in the subject.

A basic medical graduate is required to justify the clinical features of endocrinology diseases like hypothyroidism, acromegaly, Diabetes mellitus and tetany. Thus in physiology, understanding of the concept involving mechanism of action of hormones is essential component for understanding

the planning treatment protocols as well.[6] This study was conducted to evaluate the perception of 1st year MBBS students regarding the use of CWPs as an educational tool for enhancing their self-learning and adjunct tool for creative learning.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted at Mamata Medical College, Khammam among 1st year MBBS students in April 2024. Ethical committee approval was taken (MMC/IEC/95/2024) and students were administered a consent form. There were no additional scores given to the students for their participation in the study.

The core areas of endocrine physiology were chosen and a CWP was made on four different hormones. 3 Google forms were designed namely for pre and post-test MCQ on the same competencies and another from for a feedback for the perception of students on CWP as a learning tool. Traditional didactic lectures on endocrine physiology were taken by a faculty as per the teaching schedule in April 2024. Four CWPs were designed by using MSWord with questions based

on four endocrine gland from the competencies used for MCQ. The Google forms required for the pre, post-test, feedback on CWP were all validated by the faculty in the department. The students were then informed about formative assessment on the same topics that was conducted after 10 days of the last lecture by using a Google form based MCQs and a CWP activity was also scheduled the next day. 10 groups of students were formed and a time span of 1 hour was given to solve the CWP as a group activity. After the task, a feedback form was collected using 9 closed questions to understand their perception on CWP as learning tool by using Likert scale and few open ended questions were also given to look for additional themes for learning. After a week another MCQ based questionnaire with higher order questions on the same topic was administered to evaluate if CWP kindled any interest into deep self-learning of the topics. The feedback responses were tabulated, analyzed and the scores of pre-test, post-test were analyzed by chi -square test.

Cross Word Puzzle Activity

				1A	P	1P	E	T	I	T	E
						A					
						N					
						C					
				2I		R					
	2G	A	N	G	R	E	N	E			
			S			A					
			U			S					
			L								
			4I	3R	S						
3U	R	I	N	E							
				T							
				I							
				N							
				A							

Across Down

1. Increased food crave 1. gland secreting a glucose regulating hormone
2. Dead tissue seen as complication 2. hormone regulating blood glucose
3. Sample for bedside test for glucose estimation 3. layer of eye damaged with high blood glucose
4. Hormone response elements

						1G						
						L						
						U						
			2J			C						
			1	C	R	O	M	3E	G	A	4L	Y
			A									
			W			S		P			I	
						E		I			V	
								P			E	

pertinent to the topics that were taught. Only 22.72% strongly agreed responses was obtained for time sufficiency for the activity. Nearly 90% (33.33% -strongly agreed and 57.57% - agreed) wanted such activities to be given extra credits in

regular assessment.(Table 2).The pre and post test scores showed significance of $p < 0.00001$, thus the post test scores improved after the CWP activity.(Table 2)

Figure 1: Sex wise distribution of students who responded to the pre, post-test MCQs and feedback on CWP activity

Figure 2: Perception of students about Crossword puzzle on Likert scale

Table 1: Perception of students about Crossword puzzle on Likert scale

Question on the CWP activity	Strongly Agree N (%)	Agree N (%)	Neither Agree Nor Disagree N (%)	Disagree N (%)	Strongly Disagree N (%)
Activity of crossword puzzle was interesting	29(43.93)	35(53.03)	1(1.51)	0(0.00)	1(1.51)
The puzzle in the cross word helped me to analyze and apply concepts of endocrine Physiology	24(36.36)	41(62.12)	0(0.00)	1(1.51)	0(0.00)
Group discussion in puzzle solving helps in better understanding of the topic	33(50)	33(50)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)
Puzzle like crossword motivates learning	29(43.93)	32(48.48)	4(6.06)	1(1.51)	0(0.00)
The crossword activity gave an orientation on what to focus in the topic taught	23(38.48)	38(57.57)	4(6.06)	1(1.51)	0(0.00)
The crossword activity content was pertinent to what was taught	22(33.33)	33(50)	8(12.12)	3(4.54)	0(0.00)
The time given to solve the crossword puzzle was sufficient	15(22.72)	41(62.12)	4(6.06)	6(9.09)	0(0.00)
Learned better from the topics because of the crossword puzzle	15(22.72)	38(57.57)	9(13.63)	4(6.06)	0(0.00)
Extra credits for activities like CWP	22(33.33)	38(57.57)	4(6.06)	2(3.03)	0(0.00)

Table 2: Open responses about Crossword puzzle

S.No	Responses from non-mandated open ended questions on comments on CWP
1	Open ended responses
2	Good
3	It was nice
4	Good
5	It was very useful
6	Very interesting
7.	It was fun solving the puzzle
8	Pretty good
9	It was a good experience
10	Its very useful
11	Very interesting
12	It was fun solving the puzzle
13	The activity was really interesting and because of this activity I got interest towards the topic not only that but also this activity made lecture very interesting. thank you so much for conducting this activity
14	Awesome
15	Increased Conceptual and learning of physiology
16	We want more puzzles
17	It was nice
18	It was best
19	It was a good experience
20	Good activity
21	Super
22	best
23	It was best
24	Really loved it
25	engaging
26	Great activity
27	It was a fun way of learning
28	Conduct MCQ s on all topics like yesterday.

Table 3: Effect of CWP on MCQ assessment

	below 50%	Above 50%	Marginal Row Totals
Pre Test Scores	51 (32.5) [10.53]	15 (33.5) [10.22]	66
Post Test Scores	14 (32.5) [10.53]	52 (33.5) [10.22]	66
Marginal Column Totals	65	67	132 (Grand Total)

The chi-square statistic is 41.4944. The p-value is < 0.00001.

Discussion

Medical education is expanding to newer horizons with newer teaching learning methods which are student centric and stimulate self-learning. SDL helps a student to develop critical thinking which is very much essential for a future clinician.[7] To prepare the future doctors with required skills there needs to be a strong foundation of knowledge of concepts in Physiology.

The high stimulation of brain of the millennials by social media, educational apps has to be tapped carefully and redirected for proper learning behaviour [8,9]. Andragogy facilitates an individually tailored approach for self-learning. CWP as an edutainment is used to blend with the didactic lectures for a recreational, enjoyable way of learning.[10] Designing a CWP is time consuming yet a very useful tool which can be developed in a low resource setting. It is still worth enduring the pains for the outcomes achieved in stimulating young brains for the quest of knowledge.

A similar finding in students' response was seen in the study conducted by C Bailey, et. al.[4] Students opined to conduct such engaging tasks for all topics in Physiology. Group activity of CWP also helped them to have a collaborative learning which will help them to be good team players in future, one of the goals set for an IMG.[11] The flexibility, enjoy ability in learning by a CWP is commendable. It also helps the students to focus on key information, retention of the concept and application in practice.[12-18]

This technique can be employed in online mode as well and thus can also be a part of the flipping of the classroom.[19] Thus CWP activity can harness the energy of medical youth to orient them for self-learning in a creative, retentive way essential for scoring in exams and practicing later in the future.[20] Gamification with the right tool like CWP is useful to have interactive teaching lectures, motivate self-learning and enhance knowledge of the students.

Conclusion

Student's perceptions indicated that they have received the CWP rightly and it was useful in better understanding of the key concepts in endocrine physiology.

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References

1. Gaikwad N, Tankhiwale S. Crossword puzzles: self-learning tool in pharmacology. *Perspect Med Educ.* 2012 Dec; 1(5-6):237-248.
2. Document <https://www.nmc.org.in/information-desk/for-colleges/ug-curriculum/>
3. Saxena A, Nesbitt R, Pahwa P, Mills S. Crossword puzzles: active learning in undergraduate pathology and medical education. *Arch Pathol Lab Med.* 2009 Sep;133(9):1457-62.
4. Sannathimmappa MB, Nambiar V, Aravindakshan R. Learning out of the box: Fostering intellectual curiosity and learning skills among the medical students through gamification. *J Educ Health Promot.* 2022 Mar 23;11:1-6.
5. Bailey CM, Hsu CT, DiCarlo SE. Educational puzzles for understanding gastrointestinal physiology. *Am J Physiol.* 1999 Jun; 276(6 Pt 2):S1-18.
6. Bangera, Shobith & Kumar, Latha Rajendra & Thalenjeri, Padmini. Introducing innovative crossword puzzles in undergraduate physiology teaching- learning process. *Archives of Medicine and Health Sciences.*2015(3) 127-130.
7. Nazeer MS, Ahmed Razia, Asad Mohammad Muzammil, Sami Mohammad Rehan, Hattiwale Waqas, Sreekanth Haroon Rasheed. Crossword puzzles as an active learning mode for student directed learning in anatomy teaching: Medical undergraduate perceptions. *Int J Med Res Health Sci.* 2018; 7(10):12-9. 55.
8. Boomers OD, Gen-Xers. Understanding the "New Students." *Educ Rev.* 2003; 38(4):37-47.
9. Elshami WS, Coumaravelou, Taha MHA, Mohamed Elhassan; Abuzaid, Mohamed; Al Kawas, Sausan. Bridging the Gap in Online Learning Anxiety: Generation X teaching Millennial and Z generations. *Sultan Qaboos University Medical Journal [SQUMJ].* 2021.
10. Bawazeer, G., Sales, I., Albogami, H. et al. Crossword puzzle as a learning tool to enhance learning about anticoagulant therapeutics. *BMC Med Educ.* 2022, 267.
11. Rudland JR. Learning in small groups. Dent JA, Harden RM, Eds. *A practical guide for medical teachers.* London, UK: Elsevier Churchill Livingstone. 2005:57-65.
12. Zamani P, Diparva Haghghi S, Ravanbakhsh M. The use of crossword puzzles as an educational tool. *J Adv Med Educ Prof.* 2021; 9(2):102-8. 50.
13. Shawahna R, Jaber M. Crossword puzzles improve learning of Palestinian nursing students about pharmacology of epilepsy: Results of a randomized controlled study. *Epilepsy Behav.* 2020; 106: 107024.

14. Patrick SV, Giri K, Datta VP, Kumawat D, Singh P, Matreja P. The usefulness of crossword puzzle as a self-learning tool in pharmacology. *J Adv Med Educ Prof.* 2018; 6(4):181–5.
15. Mshayisa VV. Students' perceptions of Plickers and crossword puzzles in undergraduate studies. *J Food Sci Educ.* 2020; 19(2):49–58. 52.
16. Gilani RN, Priyanka; Daigavane Pallavi, Bajaj Pavan, Mankar Nikhil, Vishnani Rozina. Crossword puzzle: An effective self-learning modality for dental undergraduates. *J Datta Meghe Inst Med Sci Univ.* 2020; 15(3):397. 53.
17. Malini M, Sudhir G, Narasimhaswamy K. Crossword puzzle as a tool to enhance learning among students in a medical school. *Natl J Physiol Pharm Pharmacol.* 2019; 9(8):793–7. 54.
18. Gupta U, Gupta NK, Sinha P, Gupta S, Mahdi F. Creative learning using crossword puzzle as learning tool for undergraduates in obstetrics and gynecology. *J Contemp Med Edu.* 2015; 3(1):36-9.
19. Yousof SM, Kaddam LA, Zayed MA. Students' Satisfaction Regarding the Application of Crossword Puzzles During the Online Teaching Practice of Medical Physiology: A Promising Experience During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Med Sci Educ.* 2023 Nov 14;34(1):125-131.
20. Mohan BS, Nambiar V, Gowda S, Arvind akshan R. Crossword puzzle: A tool for enhancing medical students learning in microbiology and immunology. *Int J Res in Med Sci.* 2018; 6(3):756-59.